

EVALUATION OF CLINICAL EXAMINATION RESULTS. POST-OPERATIVE CONDITIONS.

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According to the results of the tests, the local and general effect of the used drug depends on the age, general condition of the body, and the presence of additional diseases.

The effectiveness of the treatment was determined by evaluating the courses of the postoperative period, as well as the results of instrumental examination in the main and control groups. Evaluation of treatment results was performed within one year from the date of surgery. The speed and quality of bone tissue recovery, the degree of absorption of the used material, the rate of patient complaints and repeat visits were analyzed.

Thus, in the period from 2009 to 2019, 1301 patients who were treated for mandibular fractures were examined and treated at the City Clinical Hospital No. 7. Clinical studies were conducted on 117 patients aged 18-60 with mandibular fracture defects, of which 57 were 18-25 years old, 42 were 26-40 years old, 18 were 41-60 years old, 109 were men and 8 were women. The main and control groups were formed to evaluate the effectiveness of the use of "OsteonTMII Sollagen" in the elimination of the defect created by fractures of the lower jaw. In the main group of patients, 79 had bone defects filled with "OsteonTMII Sollagen" during surgery. The control group included patients who underwent exactly such an operation, in which, unlike the main group, "OsteonTMII Sollagen" not applied. The number of patients in the group was 38. Indicators by age and gender of the examined patients are presented in diagrams 1, 2.

Diagram 1. Diagram 2.

The analysis of short-term and long-term results of surgical treatment of patients was carried out according to the following indicators:

1. Appetite
2. Insomnia.
3. Pain in the wound.
4. Body temperature.
5. Postoperative edema and hematoma.
6. Position of seams.
7. Discharge from the wound.
8. Wound healing.

Based on the comparative evaluation of the average values of these indicators

Average Me, lower NK and higher VC indicators are presented in table 4.1. Here n is the number of patients in groups with jaw fractures.

Comparative evaluation of the clinical course of the postoperative period in patients with jaw fractures in groups.

Days	The number of patients n	Main			Control			
		Me	VK	VN	N	Me	VK	VN
Appetite								
1	10	3	3	3	10	3, 5	3	4
3	10	2	2	3	10	3	3	3
7	10	1	1	1	10	2	2	2
14	10	1	1	1	10	1	1	2
28	10	1	1	1	10	1	1	1
Insomnia								
1	10	2	2	2	10	3, 5	3	4
3	10	2	1	2	10	2	2	2
7	10	1	1	1	10	1	1	2
14	10	1	1	1	10	1	1	1
28	10	1	1	1	10	1	1	1

Body temperature								
1	10	2	2	2	10	2	2	2
3	10	1	1	2	10	2	2	2
7	10	1	1	1	10	1	1	1
14	10	1	1	1	10	1	1	1
28	10	1	1	1	10	1	1	1
Pain in the operation area								
1	10	3	3	3	10	3	3	3
3	10	2	2	3	10	3	2	3
7	10	1	1	1	10	2	1	2
14	10	1	1	1	10	1	1	1
28	10	1	1	1	10	1	1	1
Postoperative edema and hematoma								
1	10	3	3	4	10	3	3	4
3	10	3	3	3	10	3	3	3
7	10	2	2	2	10	3	2	3
14	10	1	1	1	10	2	2	2
28	10	1	1	1	10	1	1	1
Position of stitches.								
1	10	1	1	1	10	1	1	1
3	10	1	1	1	10	1	1	1
7	10	1	1	1	10	1	1	1
Discharge from the wound.								
3	10	1	1	2	10	1	1	2
7	10	1	1	1	10	1	1	1

14	10	1	1	1	10	1	1	1
28	10	1	1	1	10	1	1	1
Wound healing.								
7	10	1	1	1	10	1	1	1
14	10	1	1	1	10	1	1	1
28	10	1	1	1	10	1	1	1

2.4. table. Determination of the general and local condition of patients.

2.7. Densitometric examination indicators.

In order to determine the regeneration processes in the area of the bone defect of the patients, it was carried out on the basis of the "Image J" program, based on the optical light absorption of the tissue. Patients' orthopantomography was studied before the operation, on the 1st day, 1 month, 3 months, 6 months and 1 year after the operation. When studied by "Image J", it was observed that the optical density of the healthy bone cortical plate is up to 170, and the optical density of porous bone is around 150. The beginning of bone regeneration in the operated area was from 40±5 units to 165±5.

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